
Management of School Related Variables and Teachers' Job Effectiveness in Secondary Schools in Calabar South Local Government Area of Cross River State, Nigeria.

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Abstract

Management of school related variables and teachers' job effectiveness in secondary schools in Calabar South Local Government Area, Cross River State was the main thrust of this study. Four research questions were raised, and four hypotheses were formulated to direct the study. The descriptive survey design was adopted for the study while the total population of 208 secondary school teachers in Calabar South Local Government Area were selected for the study using census technique. A questionnaire titled "Management of School Related Variables and Teachers' Job Effectiveness in Secondary School Questionnaire (MSRVTJESSQ)" designed by the researcher was used as instrument to collect data from the respondents. The null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance using Pearson Product Moment Correlation, Independent t-test, and One-Way Analysis of Variance statistical techniques where applicable. It was found that; managing class size, school management style, and school location has a significant influence on teachers' job effectiveness respectively in Calabar South Local Government Area of Cross River State. It was recommended amongst others that; school principals should ensure that they adopt a more contingent management style where different situations will warrant the use of different technique; and the recommended teacher-pupils' ratio of 1:35 should be maintained.

Keywords: *Management, School Related Variables, Teachers, Job Effectiveness, Teachers' Job Effectiveness, Secondary Schools.*

1. Introduction

The goal of every organization is to attain stated objectives using available human and material resources. The school is a formal organization and consequently, it has stated objectives to attain. According to Owan (2012), teachers are great determinants of the success or failure of any school because, they are the roots of any tree (any educational system). It is through the roots that the tree gets nutrient to all its branches, without the roots being alive or in a healthy state, the tree will die or wither gradually (Owan, 2012). From the above assertion, it implies that teachers are the mainstay of the educational system and can contribute to the furtherance or hindrance of the school from achieving stated objectives. Teachers provide instruction (nutrients) to the learners to help them develop into a fully nourished (useful) individuals. Therefore, there is need for teachers to be effective for the school system to stay alive and healthy.

Teachers' job effectiveness refers to the degree at which teachers are discharging their pedagogical duties in the school, which has the capacity to support or pull down the school from reaching its ends. Teachers' effectiveness has been one of the most important indicators used to assess the effectiveness of any school.

It has been observed that many secondary school teachers in Calabar South Local Government Area of Cross River State, negligently absent themselves from school; some exhibit poor attitudes towards punctuality and proper record keeping. Many secondary school teachers were also observed, and reported by many parents, to be engaging in sexual relationships with some senior secondary school students of opposite gender. This was more predominant with irresponsible male teachers who slept and raped several students who refused to formally accept their unhealthy relationship. These poor and ineffective attitudes displayed by these teachers have caused a lot of problems for families especially mothers, who are usually blamed by their husband. Also, these negative attitudes displayed by teachers have not only succeeded in affecting the smooth running of the school, it has gone beyond to affect students' academic performance in classroom and standardized examinations that are regulated by bodies such as NECO, WAEC, JAMB and so on.

According to Avwerosuo (2017), there are slight improvement in the condition of service of the teachers; this include relatively prompt payment of teachers' salaries, increment of teacher's salaries following the recent minimum wage pronouncement, promotion of teachers in some quarters and building of classroom blocks and few offices being a project recently embarked upon by the state Government (Avwerosuo, 2017). With all these developments in place, one expects secondary school teachers to be effective in performing their jobs. However, the reverse is the case in the area of study. This has made the researcher assess whether the management of school related variables has an influence on teachers' job effectiveness.

School related variables refer to the different characteristics and unique attributes that can be observed from school to school, and which makes one school different from the other. For instance, some school are publicly owned, while others are privately owned. According to Arop and Owan (2018), institutional variables remain an important area in the school system that should be studied and well managed to enhance teachers' work effectiveness. The concept of management of school related variables in this study include class size management, school management style, and management of school location.

Class size refers to the total number of students in a class that receive lesson together, interact with one another and share resources with one another within the confines of a classroom. Class size is an important factor in relation to academic performance of students. There is a consensus among various researchers and educationists that, the lower the class size or teacher-pupil ratio, the better the performance of teachers and students. This is because teachers' and students' performance decreases, as class size increases (Fabunmi, Brai-Abu & Adeniji, 2007). Thus, class size management is simply ensuring that the number of students allocated to a teacher is such that will not bulk the teacher. The prescribed teacher-students' ratio for secondary school is 1:35 (The Federal Republic of Nigeria - FRN, 2004) (i.e. one teacher to 35 students) for effective teaching and learning.

School management style refers to the methods and techniques used by the school administrator to get things done and achieve stated goals of the school. According to Akpan (2016), the success of any organization depends greatly on its leadership. The school leader (principal) should possess certain qualities that would enable him/her to perform his/her administrative tasks efficiently and effectively for the attainment of the school goals and objectives. It can be said that different schools are managed by different leaders with different personal characteristics. These differences in the characteristics of school leaders, makes the leadership of schools to vary from one school to another.

School location refers to where a school is situated or sited, it can be in a rural location, urban location, and sub-urban regions. It refers to the geographical position in which a school is built. A school can be built on a hill, a swampy environment, a sloppy area, in a rural or urban setting etc. (Arop and Owan, 2018). According to Nirav (2018), a school should be set up in a suitable atmosphere. The school location has enormous significance. It must have plenty of space with shady trees around, far away from noise of the crowded city and polluting atmosphere. There should be a calm and quiet which is conducive to teaching and learning. Thus, school location management refers to the careful decisions on how and where to site a school, and plans made to ensure that environmental hazards within such environment are eliminated from time to time.

Given the critical role that teachers play in teaching and learning, coupled with their perceived ineffectiveness in the discharge of their duties in Calabar South Local Government Area of Cross River State, is an indicator that there is a problem. This problem needs urgent attention especially, based on the evidence that students have been negatively affected in their academic performance. This study was conducted against this background, to examine school related variables and teachers' job effectiveness in secondary schools in Calabar South Local Government Area of Cross River State.

2. Literature review

The review of literature was based on empirical studies that were carried out by earlier studies. This was done to explore their findings and/or methods employed in order to gain better insights to the study.

2.1. Class size management and teachers' job effectiveness

Class size refers to the number of students in each course or classroom, specifically either the number of students being taught by individual teachers in a course or classroom, or the average number of students being taught by teachers in a school, district, or education system. Number of students per teacher is generally associated with class size and it is mainly believed that smaller classes provide a better teaching and learning.

Nizamettin and Bekir (2015), studied students per teacher and students' achievement. In the study, the data for the number of students per teacher was obtained by dividing the total number of students in high schools by the total number of teachers in high schools in every city of Turkey. The data for students' achievement was based on each city's achievement ranking on Turkey's Transition to Higher Education Exam. Spearman Rho's analysis was conducted to see if there is a correlation between these variables. The result of the analysis showed a significant correlation of $-.561$. This moderate negative correlation between the student teacher ratio and achievement revealed that the cities with greater number of students per teacher tend to have a low achievement on Turkey's Transition to Higher Education Exam. The result suggested more teachers should be hired in order to decrease the number of students per teacher so that students' achievement can enhance. The findings of Nizamettin and Bekir (2015), is related to this study because students' academic performance is one aspect of judging an effective teacher.

According to Zakrajsek, (2007), class size is not the major deterrent to positive learning environments. In fact, perception of what constitutes an acceptable class size is relative. A teacher of 150 students would love to teach the class with only 50 students, whereas someone who has just been told her class is moving from 20 to 50 may experience an overwhelming feeling of dread. The number of students is important, but the attitude of

the teacher in dealing with the class size makes the difference. When class size increases, teachers can do many things to enhance students' learning opportunities (Zakrajsek, 2007).

2.2. School management style and teachers' job effectiveness

It is generally believed that the effectiveness of people in an organisation depends on the quality of its leadership since effective leader behaviour enables them to meet their goals (Hayward, 2005). Furthermore, leaders have a definite effect on the behaviour and outlook of their subordinates. Therefore, teachers as part of their follower roles, depend on their principals as their leaders, to encourage and motivate them. In addition, principals should provide training to new and inexperienced teachers to help prepare them adequately as effective leadership enables the entire workforce to participate in the different activities of an organisation and can also influence individual and organisational performance (Mullen, 2004).

Atsebeha (2016), examined the leadership styles adopted by school principals and their influence on the job performance of primary school teachers in the Tigray region of Ethiopia. Descriptive and inferential statistical analyses were conducted and presented in a clear and logical manner. Based on the findings of the study, it was revealed that principals and teachers indicated that all the leadership styles, except the directive leadership style, have a positive impact on the teachers' performance. Furthermore, the supportive leadership style is the most frequently used style. The data also indicated a statistically significant relationship between the job performance of teachers and the leadership styles employed by the principals.

Principals' leadership styles and teachers' job performance in senior secondary schools in Ondo State, Nigeria was investigated by Adeyemi (2011). Two instruments were used to collect data for the study. Teachers' job performance was found to be better in schools having principals using autocratic leadership style than in schools having principals using democratic or laissez-faire leadership styles. It was recommended that school principals should imbibe a mixture of autocratic and democratic styles of leadership in their school administration in order to enhance better job performance among teachers.

2.3. School location management and teachers' job effectiveness

School location refers to the place, in relation to other areas in the physical environment (rural or urban), where the school is sited (Joseph and Emmanuel, 2017). According to Arop and Owan (2018) school location refers to where a school is situated or sited, it can be in a rural location, urban location, and sub-urban regions. It can be added that school location refers to the geographical position in which a school was built. A school can be built on a hill, a swampy environment, a sloppy area, in a rural or urban setting and so on.

Nsa, Offiong, Udo, and Ikot, (2014) assessed the relationship between school environmental variables and teachers job performance in Agricultural Science. The study adopted a correlational survey design. A sample size of 300 students were randomly selected and used for the study. Data were analysed, and null hypotheses tested using PPMC. The findings indicated that there was significant relationship between school location and teachers job performance in Agricultural Science.

In a related study, Meremikwu and Enuokoha (2010) assessed the effects of school variables on mathematics teachers' effectiveness in both public and private schools in Cross River State, Nigeria. The study utilised a quasi-experimental design and a sample of 600 teachers were selected using multi-stage random method. The results of the study showed that

mathematics teachers' effectiveness was significantly dependent on the treatment, school type and school location but not on teachers' gender. Also, all the interactions of the treatment, gender, school type, and school location were statistically significant in explaining mathematics teachers' effectiveness. In the urban areas, the authors reported that teachers in the experimental group in private schools achieved significantly higher than their counterparts in the public schools.

3. Statement of the problem

It can be recalled that the secondary schools were established for the society as a means of producing quality students and providing good inputs to the tertiary institutions. It was expected that everybody in the secondary school system including the principals, teachers and non-teaching staff, play active roles in modifying the behaviour of secondary school students through effective teaching and learning. In an ideal situation, teachers who are the main drivers of the curriculum implementation process, supposed to discharge their duties with all amount of effectiveness and willingness for the school to achieve stated goals.

Sadly, many teachers in Calabar South Local Government Area of Cross River State, exhibit poor and ineffective attitudes to work; especially in terms of record keeping, punctuality, attendance to classes, self-discipline, writing of notes of lesson, and so on. These poor attitudes are unacceptable because they contribute in bringing down the school system and limiting it from achieving its objectives. The Government and other NGOs to improve teachers' effectiveness, have organized retraining and development workshops for teachers, improved teachers' salary structure, payment of teachers' salaries in a timely manner, and so on. Despite all these efforts made, many teachers in secondary schools in Calabar South Local Government Area are adamant and unwilling to improve.

The poor performance of students in classroom and standardized examinations such as WAEC, NECO, GCE, JAMB etc. in recent times is an indicator that the teachers who teach such students should be questioned in terms of their effectiveness. The quality of students supplied by secondary schools to the tertiary institutions have also witness a decline. As many secondary school graduates enter tertiary institutions without the ability to read and write. Consequently, this has also affected the quality of graduates produced from the tertiary institutions yearly, as well as the economic productivity of Nigeria in general.

The need for teachers to be effective cannot be overemphasized. The major problem of this study is that; could management of school related variables such as school infrastructural facilities, class size, school management style, and school location be responsible for teachers' job effectiveness? An attempt to answer this question, gave rise to this study.

4. Purpose of the study

The general purpose of this study was to examine management of school related variables and teachers' job effectiveness in secondary schools in Calabar South Local Government Area, Cross River State. Specifically, this study sought to examine how the influence of:

- i.** Class size management on teachers' job effectiveness.
- ii.** School management style on teachers' job effectiveness.
- iii.** School location management on teachers' job effectiveness.

5. Statement of hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated to guide the study.

- i.** Class size management has no significant influence on teachers' job effectiveness.
- ii.** School management style has no significant influence on teachers' job effectiveness.

- iii. School location management has no significant influence on teachers' job effectiveness.

6. Methods

The design adopted for the study was descriptive survey design. According to Idaka and Anagbogu (2012) descriptive survey design is used to find out what situations, events attitudes or opinions are occurring in a population. It tries to address issues of distribution of some phenomena in a population or among sub groups of a population. The focus of this design is to ascertain facts and not to establish or test theory. This design was considered appropriate because, the study purports to use the information obtained through questionnaires, in describing observed phenomena.

The population of this study included all the 208 teachers distributed across the eight (8) public secondary schools in Calabar South Local Government Area. Census technique was used to select the entire population of 208 public secondary school teachers available in the eight public secondary schools in Calabar South Local Government Area of Cross River State. Census technique is used when the population is small and can be studied totally.

The instrument used for data collection was a questionnaire designed by the researcher and was tagged: "Management of School Related Variables and Teachers' Job Effectiveness in Secondary School Questionnaire (MSRVTJESSQ)." The instrument was divided into two sections. Section A was used to elicit demographic data of respondents; while section B elicited information on school related variables such as infrastructural facilities and school management style, as well as teachers' job effectiveness.

The instrument received its face, content and construct validity from two experts in measurement and evaluation unit, Department of Educational Foundations, University of Calabar, Calabar. These experts ensured that the items were relatively clear in contents and arrangements thereby avoiding irrelevant information and ambiguity. The instruments were administered to the respondents in their respective schools personally with the assistance of two research assistants. The 208 teachers were used to assess the management of school related variables, while 208 senior secondary school students were used to assess the job effectiveness of their English language teachers. At the end of the process, copies of the instruments were retrieved from the respondents for analysis.

To ease the process of data preparation, each copy of the instruments was assigned numerical value for each rater, then a key was developed to guide the coding process of data collected from the respondent. The statements on the instruments were sorted out based on the variables they were purported to measure. The data were scored appropriately for positive and negative worded items.

The procedure used in the analysis of data was that each hypothesis used for the study was stated clearly. Both the independent and dependent variables were identified. The statistical technique employed for data analysis were identified as shown below:

Hypothesis one

Class size management has no significant influence on teachers' job effectiveness.

Independent variable: Class size management

Dependent variable: Teachers' job effectiveness.

Statistical tool: Independent t-test

Hypothesis two

School management style has no significant influence on teachers' job effectiveness.

Independent variable: school management style

Dependent variable: Teachers' job effectiveness.

Statistical tool: One-Way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA)

Hypothesis three

School location management has no significant influence on teachers' job effectiveness.

Independent variable: School location

Dependent variable: Teachers' job effectiveness.

Statistical tool: Independent t-test

7. Presentation of result

The results of this study were presented according to the hypotheses formulated. The presentation and interpretation of results was done as follows.

7.1. Hypothesis one

Class size management has no significant influence on teachers' job effectiveness. The result of the analysis using independent t-test is presented in Table 1.

TABLE 1:

Independent t-test analysis of the influence of class size management on teachers' job effectiveness (N = 208)

Variables	Class size management	N	Mean	Std. Dev,	t-cal.	p-value
Teachers' job effectiveness	Small (1 - 35 students)	109	18.69	4.44	12.846	.000*
	Large (36 students and above)	99	11.29	3.78		

*Significant at $p < .05$; $df = 206$;

The result above shows that the p-value .000* is less than .05 level of significance at 206 degrees of freedom. By this result, the null hypothesis was rejected, and the conclusion is that; class size management has a significant influence on teachers' job effectiveness in Calabar South Local Government Area, Cross River State. The result also indicates that teachers' job effectiveness in small class sizes (1 – 35 students) was better (mean= 18.69), than in large class sizes (36 students and above) with mean (11.29).

7.2. Hypothesis three

School management style has no significant influence on teachers' job effectiveness. The result of the analysis is presented in Table 2.

TABLE 2:
One-way analysis of variance results of the influence of school management style and teachers' job effectiveness (N = 208)

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	p-value
Between Groups	3865.68	2	1932.84	157.65	.000*
Within Groups	2513.44	205	12.26		
Total	6379.11	207			

*Significant at $p < .05$

The results presented in Table 2 indicates that the p-value .000* is less than .05 level of significance. With this result, the null hypothesis is rejected while the alternate hypothesis is upheld. The conclusion is that; school management style has a significant influence on teachers' job effectiveness. In determining whether there is a significant difference in the mean of the various school management styles, the Fisher's Least Square Difference multiple comparison test was performed as presented in Table 3 below.

TABLE 3:
Fisher's Least Square Difference of Multiple Comparisons

Dependent Variable: Teachers' job effectiveness

(I) Mgt. styles	(J) Mgt. styles	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.
Autocratic style	Democratic style	-10.18*	.5993	.000
	Laissez-faire style	-3.22*	.6230	.000
Democratic style	Autocratic style	10.18*	.5993	.000
	Laissez-faire style	6.97*	.5759	.000
Laissez-faire style	Autocratic style	3.22*	.6230	.000
	Democratic style	-6.97*	.5759	.000

*. The mean difference is significant at 0.05 level.

The results presented in Table 3 shows that; at .05 level of significance, there is a significant mean difference in the management styles utilized in public secondary schools in Calabar South Local Government Area. The results further revealed specifically that; there is a significant difference between autocratic style and democratic style (Mean difference (MD) = -10.18*). There is a significant difference between autocratic style and laissez-faire style (MD = -3.22*). There is a significant difference between democratic style and laissez-faire style (MD = 6.97*). Generally, it was concluded that; democratic style had a higher mean value, followed by laissez-faire, and autocratic styles in that order.

7.3. Hypothesis three

School location management has no significant influence on teachers' job effectiveness. The result of the analysis is presented in Table 4.

TABLE 4:
Independent t-test analysis of the influence of school location on teachers' job effectiveness (N = 208)

Variables	School Location	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	t-cal.	p-value
Teachers' job effectiveness	Conducive locations	102	19.18	4.16	14.470	.000*
	Unconducive locations	106	11.31	3.67		

*Significant at $p < .05$; $df = 206$;

The result above shows that the p-value .000* is less than .05 level of significance at 206 degrees of freedom. By this result, the null hypothesis was rejected, and it was concluded that; school location has a significant influence on teachers' job effectiveness in Calabar South Local Government Area, Cross River State. The results also revealed that teachers' job effectiveness was higher in conducive locations (mean = 19.18; SD = 4.16) than in unconducive locations (mean = 11.31; SD = 3.67).

8. Discussion of findings

8.1. *Class size management and teachers' job effectiveness*

It was established through the findings of this study that class size management has a significant influence on teachers' job effectiveness in Calabar South Local Government Area of Cross River State. This finding agrees with Nizamettin and Bekir (2015) whose study showed a significant correlation of -.561. This moderate negative correlation between the student teacher ratio and achievement revealed that the cities with greater number of students per teacher tend to have a low achievement on Turkey's Transition to Higher Education (Exam). The result suggested more teachers should be hired in order to decrease the number of students per teacher so that students' achievement can enhance. The findings of Nizamettin and Bekir (2015), is related to the finding of this study because students' academic performance is one aspect of judging an effective teacher. Zakrajsek analysed that; a teacher of 150 students would love to teach the class with only 50 students, whereas someone who has just been told her class is moving from 20 to 50 may experience an overwhelming feeling of dread. In line with this assertion of Zakrajsek, the findings of this study revealed that teachers in small class sizes (1-35 students) were more effective than those with large class sizes (36 students and above).

8.2 *School management style and teachers' job effectiveness*

It was revealed through the findings of this study that; school management style has a significant influence on teachers' job effectiveness. The finding of this study agrees with the finding of Atsebeha (2016), which revealed that; all the leadership styles, except the directive leadership style, have a positive impact on the teachers' performance. The result also indicated a statistically significant relationship between the job performance of teachers and the leadership styles employed by the principals

Principals' leadership styles and teachers' job performance in senior secondary schools in Ondo State, Nigeria was investigated by Adeyemi (2011). Teachers' job performance was found to be better in schools having principals using autocratic leadership style than in schools having principals using democratic or laissez-faire leadership styles. It was recommended that school principals should imbibe a mixture of autocratic and democratic styles of leadership in their school administration in order to enhance better job performance among teachers. The finding of this study further corroborates the

recommendation made by Adeyemi by disclosing that teachers' job effectiveness was higher in schools where the managers adopted democratic management styles, followed by those whose managers adopted laissez-faire and autocratic management styles.

8.3. School location management and teachers' job effectiveness

The finding emanating from this study established also that there is a significant influence of school location on teachers' job effectiveness. This finding corroborates the finding of Nsa, Offiong, Udo, and Ikot, (2014), which indicated that there was significant relationship between school location and teachers job performance in Agricultural Science. The study of Meremikwu and Enuokoha (2010) showed that mathematics teachers' effectiveness was significantly dependent on the treatment, school type and school location but not on teachers' gender. Also, all the interactions of the treatment, gender, school type, and school location were statistically significant in explaining mathematics teachers' effectiveness. The results of this study agree with the result of Meremikwu and Enuokoha (2010), because it was revealed through the finding of the present study that teachers' job effectiveness was higher in schools in conducive locations than in schools sited in unconducive locations.

9. Conclusion

In conclusion, there exist an influence of management of school related variables on teachers' job effectiveness in secondary schools in Calabar South Local Government Area, Cross River State. The number of students in a class influences teachers' job effectiveness. Teachers who teach small class sizes are more effective than those teaching large class sizes. School management style influence teachers' job effectiveness with democratic style having the most influence followed by laissez-faire and then autocratic. Where a school is located influences teachers' job effectiveness. Teachers who teach in schools located in conducive environment are more effective than those whose schools are in unconducive environment.

10. Recommendations

- The following recommendations were stated following the outcome of the findings;
- i.** School principals should ensure that they adopt a more contingent management style where different situations will warrant the use of different techniques. This will help eliminate conflict and ensure that principals relate cordially with all teachers.
 - ii.** Class sizes in secondary schools should be checked, and the recommended teacher-students' ratio of 1:35 should be maintained. More teachers should also be employed to address shortages.
 - iii.** Schools should be sited in areas that are accessible by supervisors that are not too far from residences and yet not too close to noisy places such as markets, factories, churches and so on.

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